

FORMATION OF LOCAL BUDGET REVENUES AND PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT PROSPECTS

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The current state of reforming the budget system and rational and efficient use of state budget funds in the Republic of Uzbekistan makes it difficult for economists to find solutions to a number of new problems. In fact, at the current stage of the development of the budget system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the current public finance system does not meet modern requirements and does not allow for an objective and reliable assessment of budget expenditures related to the ongoing budget policy, state programs adopted in the medium term, and the introduction of internationally recognized methods of budget planning. Problems such as slowness are evident today.

In the medium-term development strategy of Uzbekistan, important tasks such as increasing the revenue base of local budgets, reforming expenditure systems, ensuring their financial independence, and creating a competitive environment between regions are defined. While thinking about the development of the regions, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev says: "Local budgets are not enough to finance sustainable socio-economic development of regions" ¹The reforms implemented in the financial and budget system of our country feel the need to further increase the capabilities of local budgets in the context of the aggravation of regional economic problems.

World experience in the development of the budget system makes it possible to see that the budget system of economically developed countries is as decentralized as possible. The competencies of the levels of public finance are delimited, which allows each level to independently determine a budget, implement a tax policy, and local budgets are not included in federal budgets. This shows the relative independence of the regions from the center and the possibility of minimizing the redistribution processes in the fiscal system, which contributes to the economic growth and competitiveness of the regions.

Without an effective fiscal policy in any country, without ensuring socio-economic development, the ultimate goal - a high standard of living of the population cannot be achieved. Today, radical reforms aimed at liberalization,

¹ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of activity of every leader. Report at the extended meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers, January 14, 2017, dedicated to the main results of socio-economic development of our country in 2016 and the most important priorities of the economic program for 2017. -Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2017. - 104p

structural change, innovation and modernization are being carried out in all sectors of our economy.

The state budget system plays a special role in ensuring sustainable economic growth and deepening economic reforms in the country. It should be noted that all states apply to taxes in the formation of the necessary funds to ensure development through the continuous and full implementation of their functions and responsibilities. Therefore, in today's world practice, no method other than taxes has been used to generate the financial resources needed to perform the functions of the state. How successfully do we analyze the national economy as a whole, use the factors of its further development, reduce inflation, increase foreign economic activity, integrate into the world economy and develop the national economy in a balanced and rapid manner in an innovative economy and ensure balance of payments stability increase depends on the effectiveness of macroeconomic policies and science-based reforms.

At the level of local budgets, fundamental strengthening of the revenue base of local budgets by combining them with special types of taxes and other mandatory payments, exclusion of regional, city and district budgets from subsidies and gradual implementation are the priority tasks of tax-budget policy, budgets with high incomes reducing the dependence on the distribution, based on this, solving the issues of socio-economic development of the regions by the local state authorities is defined as the increase of land resources and the determination of additional reserves on a systematic basis, and the increase of local budget revenues.

The development of scientific proposals and practical recommendations is of great importance in the implementation of measures to increase the income of local budgets, achieve effective use of local budget expenses, ensure the sustainable development of regions, and further increase the financial independence and responsibility of local government bodies.

Ensuring the stability of revenues of local budgets, as well as effective use of local budgets' expenses, depends on both economic and legal factors. Some economists recognize that these factors can be achieved by increasing the powers and responsibilities of local government bodies, while some economists recognize that they can be achieved by achieving proportionality between revenues and expenditures. local budget revenues, on the one hand, are the result of the distribution of the value of the gross domestic product among the participants of the production process, on the other hand, this value is considered and it serves to form a fund of local importance.

Economically independent activities of local budgets are characterized by their own sources of income. Local budgets should have enough financial means to solve their various tasks in their territory. In conclusion, the following could be determined:

1. Planning of local budget expenditures taking into account the natural and economic potential of the regions, ensuring the participation of People's Deputies, Regional, District, City Councils and the general public in the control over the implementation of approved expenditures is considered important for their effectiveness. Ensuring engagement and awareness of deputy councils and the general public on performance. Another important aspect in this regard is to re-study the activities of local authorities and management bodies and their related legal norms, and to pay attention to the issues of expanding their powers in the budget sphere.
2. It is important in this regard to increase the responsibility and strengthen the responsibility of local state authorities, finance and tax authorities for ensuring the effective execution of local budget expenditures in a timely manner, targeted financing, development of infrastructure and social sphere objects and maintaining them at an appropriate level. Implementation of specific performance indicators and assigning incentives or accountability based on performance or non-performance.
3. Ensuring the effective implementation of local budget expenditures consists first of all in the correct and rational planning of this expenditure system. In this case, it is necessary to pay attention to the correct and truthful structure of the budget system's analytical reports on the results achieved in the previous year and the results expected in the current year, the registers of expenditure obligations created by the budget organization, the recipients of budget funds and the distributors of budget funds, budget order reports, and the organization of the process. It is also important to make this information transparent, open and understandable to everyone.
4. It is necessary to achieve full and targeted fulfillment of the planned indicators of local budget expenditures for each type and item of expenditures.
5. In ensuring effective execution of local budget expenditures, we should not focus on the aspects of saving funds without using them, but ensure their social and economic effectiveness. After all, it is important not to forget that expenses that are not funded in time and in the right amount may cause various negative consequences later.

6. It is necessary to increase the role of local financial bodies in the implementation of the budget, to pay special attention to the values operating in their system. In particular, it is necessary to impose personal responsibility aimed at results in relation to the leading employees working in the system.

7. The creation of a system of legal norms imposing special personal responsibility on their leaders and employees of the financial department for the effective and rational use of budget funds in budget organizations will serve their effectiveness. It is expedient to pay special attention to this aspect in the issues of increasing the personal responsibility of every executive employee, which is currently demanded by the head of our state.

8. Existence of excessive centralization in the planning of local budgets, as a result of which the sense of personal responsibility of local governing bodies in the implementation of projects for the socio-economic development of the regions is not felt, and decisions regarding their obligations regarding expenses are made without taking into account the possibility of financing. Of course, as a result of this, the desire for an effective result is reduced.

Programs (plans) for the development of the revenue potential of the territory may include a set of measures and the following areas of strategy and development:

- Improving the budget and budget process by increasing the validity and accuracy of budget planning, reducing the number of revisions of budget parameters, moving to treasury budget execution systems, and ensuring transparency of the budget process;
- In accordance with the state concept of management and the result of creating the conditions, the transition to budget planning, oriented to the result (BOR), in the framework of medium-term financial planning only in the region, and in municipalities in order to provide high-quality budget services is the least cost of budget funds;
- Develop tax and revenue bases of local budgets, including: developing a set of measures to increase tax potential; the development and implementation of measures to reduce tax arrears - including bankruptcy due to the budget; increasing income on the use of property owned by the municipality, accounting for the income (profit) of the municipal unitary enterprises;
- Streamlining inter-budgetary relations in part of the rationalization of income distribution between the levels of the budget system, and in the development of budget regulation systems, in the framework of which it is proposed to abandon the strategy of ineffective universal equalization of

regional budget revenues and move on to a polarized development strategy, to create conditions that are stimulating subjects:

- Increase the efficiency of use of state and municipal property in the framework of the development and implementation of a medium-term strategy for the management of municipal property through the development of an efficiency indicator for the management and use of municipal property, inventory and keeping records (cadastres) of land, municipal property; introducing property valuation systems physically on a market basis:

Improving municipal debt management: organizing the accounting for total municipal debt; compliance. the parameter is the budget deficit, debt burden, the maximum amount of expenditure on municipal debt servicing, established by federal legislation;

